

D4.1

Evolution of Cu metallization microstructure during electro-thermal ageing

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Abstract	Plastic deformation of Cu metallization in power devices results from a combination of heat and thermomechanical stress, mainly produced by the difference in CTE between the metal and the semiconductor and oxides. Using electron microscopy, we found that the deformation mechanisms implying dislocation activities explain a minor portion of the changes endured by the copper. It is therefore supposed that pore formation and cracks growth result from another mechanism, probably grain boundary accelerated diffusion.
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Editor

Liz Karanja (CNRS)

Contributors (ordered according to beneficiary numbers)

Marc Legros (CNRS)

Reviewers

Cedric Corley-Wiciak (ESRF)

André Clausner (IKTS)

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Executive Summary

Ageing of Copper metallization is one of the main reliability concerns for high-end power devices. In the AddMorePower project, the damage induced by thermomechanical stresses on the Cu films and lines are studied through specific set-ups developed by KAI and called polyheaters. Those reproduce the thermomechanical cyclic stresses endured by a power device and due to the difference in Coefficient of Thermal Expansion (CTE) between the semiconductor base and the metal connections. WP4 is devoted to electron microscopy and the microstructure of Cu films and lines has been monitored through Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) and Transmission Electron Microscopy (TEM). This report is the deliverable 4.1, regrouping the results obtained after 20 months.

We found that dislocation plasticity, while active above 150-200°C, accounts for minimal changes in the microstructure. This activity does not change the grain structure but mainly the interior of the grain through the development of a well-defined cell structure in which the mobile dislocations fade out over successive cycles. The development of a pore structure that coalesces over cycling may be better explained by a high Grain Boundary (GB) diffusion and the inability of grains to cope with tensile strain incompatibilities through "classical" GB mechanisms (sliding, coupling, rotation). This pinning of the GBs could be the result of local chemical segregation, but the TEM techniques employed to search for GB concentration of impurities failed to do so, probably because of the insufficient accuracy of the method in regards to the very low concentrations searched.

Mid-way in this project, these results partly fulfilled the initial objectives, however some deeper analyses (dislocation density, GB misorientations) are underway, especially through novel in-situ TEM experiments where unique devices, developed in this project, will be tested.

A more systematic comparison of results obtained with X-Ray techniques (WP3) regarding Cu metallization are also planned for the remaining of the AddMorePower project.

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Chapter 1 Introduction

This main goal of task 4.3 of the AddMorePower project (to which this deliverable belongs) is to characterize the relevant deformation mechanisms affecting the copper metallizations of GaN-based power devices during thermomechanical stress. The ultimate goal of the project is to gain insights into the materials degradation phenomena. As-processed and aged structures (structures that endured cyclic thermomechanical stress) have been analysed in electron microscopes (transmission (TEM), or Scanning (SEM)) and FIB (Focused Ion Beam) with a focus on grain boundaries, dislocation densities and dislocation density gradients. Critical microstructural features and regions within the metallization layers, which may stand as stress concentrators, facilitating materials degradation, will be identified.

1.1 Devices investigated

To mimic the degradation undergone by thick metallizations in actual devices, KAI has developed polyheaters that are Si-based chips possessing the same Cu metallizations as functional power semiconductors (Moser et al., 2022). Several types of polyheaters were provided to this use case, with different Cu films. Those electrodeposited Cu films are classified as type A to C, these letters referring to microstructures with small grains and high impurities (type A) to large grains and low impurities (type C). Only Type A films that develop a pore structure along cycling will be investigated here. Two chip layouts are shown in Figure 1-1 below. The most standard set-up consists in a central pad with dimensions of $700 \times 700 \mu\text{m}^2$, that sees temperature swings between 100 and 400°C , when the polyheater endures $200 \mu\text{s}$ current pulses length followed by 1s cooling time. This central pad was the main region of interest for us. In this work, we exclusively present the analyses on the polyheaters with fine grains with more impurities (Type A Cu film). The cycled polyheaters, all with a copper thickness of $20 \mu\text{m}$ were sometimes electropolished to a reduced thickness of $5 \mu\text{m}$ to facilitate the TEM sample preparation (Moser et al., 2021).

To assess the effect of the cycles of the changes in the microstructure chips cycled to 1000 and 2000 cycles were provided.

A different polyheater “pan-flute” whereby the region of interest is a long Cu line with 90° angles promoting stress concentration was stressed to 10,000 cycles to ensure that cracks propagated through the metallization. The thickness of this film is $5 \mu\text{m}$.

Figure 1-1: Optical microscope images the two polyheater layouts investigated (a) is the standard chip and (b) is the “pan-flute” polyheater.

1.2 Experimental protocol

1.2.1 SEM and EBSD observations

Ahead of the project, extensive experiments have been carried out by KAI to study the behaviour of the grain microstructure of polyheaters along thermomechanical cycling (current injection through 200 μ s pulses followed by 200 ms cooling time, Max temperature \approx 450°C)(Kleinbichler et al., 2021).

Figure 1-2: Left: SEM, EBSD IPFz, and KAM maps of polyheater surface after 1, 1000 and 5000 cycles. Right: proportion of HAGB, twins and LAGB extracted from the previous maps (maps and graph courtesy of M. Reisinger, KAI GmbH)

From this analysis, it can be seen that in this type-A microstructure (small grains), grain growth is limited, pores appear at GB and triple junctions and seem to grow until cracks form, spanning several grains (Figure 1-2). Their propagation towards the semiconductor base eventually occurs with additional cycles, but etching of the upper surface is needed to follow this down to the bottom of the 20 μ m thick Cu film (Moser et al., 2021). This analysis also reveals that Low Angle Grain Boundaries emerge in the structure along cycling, mainly inside the grains (delimited by High Angle Grain Boundaries) (Figure 1-2).

1.2.2 TEM and TEM sample preparation

To gain further insights on the relevant deformation mechanisms active in different Cu layers, post-mortem observations (on pristine or cycled polyheaters) and in-situ (heating inside the microscope) thermal cycling were performed in the TEM. Additional automated crystallographic mapping (ACOM) analyses on as-deposited and aged Cu layers to provide information on the local misorientation gradients near grain boundaries and voids in the metallization layer, while EELS measurements will give information on segregation of elements in their vicinity.

The success of the TEM investigations is greatly driven by the sample preparation protocols. The samples varied in accordance to the different tests.

Sample preparation can be carried out through different ways, depending on the type of analysis one wants to carry out. To observe post-mortem structures, a lamella extracted by FIB from the Cu metallization only may suffice. However, FIB lamellae are usually 5-10 μ m high, and only a portion of the total metallization (20 μ m) can be observed this way. To partly reproduce the thermo-mechanical stress arising from the difference of CTE (coefficient of Thermal Expansion) between Cu and Si, a bilayer TEM sample containing both materials has to be prepared. The following types of samples have been prepared so far and will be described in the next paragraphs:

- Conventional TEM lamellae (100-300 nm thick) for simple microstructural analysis of the grain structures)
- In situ TEM FIB lamellae (additional silicon layer depth for stress implementation)
- Ultra-thin lamellae (<100 nm for chemical composition analysis)
- Mechanical polished cross section lamellae (additional silicon layer for stress implementation)

1.2.2.1 Conventional and in-situ TEM lamellae preparation

The majority of the TEM samples observed in this study were prepared in a Helios 600 FIB/SEM from FEI (now Thermofisher) from previously electropolishing-thinned Cu metallization. The FIB allows the location and the precise preparation of cross section lamellae from specific microstructural features. The main drawback of the FIB milling is the damage artefacts arising from the use of fast Ga⁺ ions during milling: irradiation defects (dislocation loops) and Ga implantation into the foils hinder the observation of "real" microstructural features (especially dislocations) in the as processed or cycled samples (Legros et al., 2024). Another issue is the small area (typically 10 μm long x 5 μm deep) of the FIB-prepared electron transparent lamella (Figure 1-3).

To reduce this irradiation damage, the classic lamella (10 x 5 μm) and the in-situ lamella (20 x 15 μm) are initially prepared by FIB (classical lift-out technique) and the final polishing steps on a precision ion polishing system (PIPS II) from Gatan. This machine has been bought in the frame of the Add More Power project in December 2023.

The PIPS polishes the sample with an argon ion beam that reduces the implantation/irradiation artefacts and greatly reduces the sample preparation time particularly for the larger in-situ samples. This ion milling system also has an additional low energy range (100-500V) that is particularly adapted to reduce Ga⁺ induced artefacts generated during FIB milling.

Figure 1-3: Sketch of the dimensions of the in-situ TEM lamellas prepared by FIB

The different milling parameters such as the milling angle, the ion beam energy and the beam modulation in the PIPS II had to be optimized for Cu films. Several polishing combinations were attempted, and it was found that the best outcome (flat, thin lamella, with less irradiation damage) is given by the following polishing steps.

Step	Voltage	Angle	Time	Sector	Beam modulation
1	500V	±7	4mins	Stationery	Backside polishing
2	500V	±7	10mins	30°	Frontside polishing
3	300V	±7	15mins	30°	Frontside polishing

Table 1: The optimized PIPS II parameters for the final polishing step of the copper films.

Figure 1-4: TEM images at different polishing steps (a) is observed after the first step, the lamella is still thick (b) shows the presence of the irradiation artefacts when the polishing step 2 was stopped halfway and (c) is the microstructure after the entire duration of the recipe of Table 1. Red arrows point to the same region, thinner and containing less irradiation damage after low kV Ar+ ion polishing.

1.2.2.2 Mechanically polished samples

The traditional TEM cross section samples are an effective way of mimicking the thermomechanical stresses induced in the metallic film during classical wafer curvature experiments (Karanja, 2024). These cross-sections are mechanically polished using a tripod polisher. This method consists in polishing a wedge, aiming at obtaining electron transparency in the thin part of this wedge.

Figure 1-5: Example of the preparation of mechanically polished TEM cross-section lamellae and their final dimensions. a) Initial configuration, b) glueing of two pieces using epoxy glue, c) Wedge obtained through tripod polishing parallel to the interface.

However, the thickness of the Cu layer and its higher atomic mass in comparison to Silicon makes it nearly impossible to polish the entire Cu film to transparency, even using PIPSII final polishing. Instead of the entire Cu cross section (20 μm) some partial sections of about 10 μm (Figure 1-6) are transparent enough to be observed.

Figure 1-6: A low magnification TEM image showcasing the milling of parts of the copper foil after the final ion polishing stages.

Despite this being a time-consuming process, the advantage is having a large part of the substrate to generate sufficient thermomechanical stresses in the foil during the in-situ heating experiments. We took care of looking at parts of the Cu film directly attached to the substrate and not those shielded from thermomechanical stress by milling holes randomly produced during milling, such as the ones observed in Figure 1-6.

TEM observations were then carried out on a JEOL 2010 HC (Conventional and in-situ, high contrast), on a Philips (now ThermoFisher) CM20FEG (ACOM ASTAR), and on a FEI (now ThermoFisher) Tecnai F20 (image corrected, chemical analysis). All observations were made at 200 kV.

Chapter 2 Microstructural evolution of copper films

This chapter aims at giving a summary of the microstructural evolution of thick copper films after repetitive short heat pulses. The degradation of the Cu film with increasing number of cycles has been previously investigated using advanced techniques such as HR-EBSD, ex-situ and in-situ dark field X-ray microscopy. The advanced TEM investigation presented here additionally aims to corroborate some of the results obtained from these prior investigations as well as providing insights on which deformation mechanisms might be responsible for this behaviour.

2.1 Pristine and cycled films

2.1.1 Microstructure of pristine films

The cross-sections prepared by mechanical polishing and FIB were investigated in a conventional TEM. The initial TEM micrographs showed the recognizable features of electrodeposited Cu type A (small grains) such as a high population of twin grain boundaries and high angle grain boundaries (HAGB) as shown in Figure 2-1. In the following, the terms "as-received" or "pristine" films may be equally used.

Figure 2-1: Low magnification TEM image of a pristine copper film.

In high magnification TEM images presented in Figure 2.2, within most of the grains, dislocations are present in the form of long lines, tangled with each other. The dislocations are arranged in a random manner i.e. there is no higher concentration of dislocations close to grain boundaries. In some grains, we also observe some cells structures (sub grain boundaries or low angle grain boundaries -LAGB-, e.g. in Figure 2-2d). So far, no particular features such as nanopores or mechanical nanotwins are observed in the microstructure.

Figure 2-2: High magnification TEM images of several grains from the pristine Cu films. a) Grain containing free dislocations and twins (orange arrows). b) Grain containing many free dislocations (blue arrows). c) Entangled dislocations (blue arrow) and twin (orange arrow) in a grain. d) Cell walls (red arrows) inside a grain.

2.1.2 Microstructure of cycled films

The Cu metallization of polyheaters was investigated at different aging times.

1000 cycles

After 1000 cycles the apparition of small pores on the surface of the film is observed. The TEM cross section observations are in agreement with the EBSD results which show that the preferred site for pore nucleation and growth are the grain boundaries.

Figure 2-3: Low magnification TEM image of the 1000 cycles Cu film . The microstructure remains quite similar to the pristine films (cp. Fig. 2-2) but we observe several small pores (marked by white arrows) at the grain boundaries.

At a higher resolution we observe that the dislocation structure within the grains has changed with fewer mobile (free) dislocations in the middle of cell structures. These cell structures, delimited by dense tangled dislocations, are present in the majority of the grains. The regions surrounding the

pores do not have any particular dislocation structures such as slip bands or heavy dislocation concentration, which attest that these pores are probably not created by dislocation plasticity.

Figure 2-4: Higher magnification TEM images showcasing the cell structures formed after 1000 cycles. There is visible reduction in the free dislocations within these cells.

2000 cycles

The main difference in the microstructure after 2000 cycles is the increase in both the number and size of the pores. The dislocation and cell structure observed is very similar to that previously observed in polyheaters cycled to 1000 cycles (cp. above).

Figure 2-5: Low magnification TEM image of Cu film cycled to 2000 cycles. The white arrows show several pores found along the grain boundaries that are significantly larger than those observed in the Figure 2-4

Figure 2-6: Higher magnification TEM images of the cell structures and mobile dislocations. The red arrows on images (a) and (b) highlight cell structures similar to those observed in Figure 2-4 (c) the black arrow shows a few mobile dislocations that are occasionally observed in the cycled films.

10,000 cycles

The surface of the “panflute polyheater” aged till 10,000 cycles is characterized by large pores and cracks. The TEM cross section milled along these large cracks shows that the pores observed are quite large in comparison to those observed after 1000 and 2000 cycles and that most of the cracks that appear the largest at the surface propagate through the metallization down to the diffusion

barrier. We observe that pores are arranged along the grain boundaries and appear to be ‘coalescing’ to form cracks. Most of the crack propagation is intergranular apart from few cases where some cracks propagated through the twins.

Figure 2-7: TEM micrograph of a Cu metallization cycled to 10,000cycles. The white arrow points to the pores/cracks.

The dislocation and cell structure within these grains are the ones where clear differences with pristine and low cycled films can be noted. The mobile dislocations observed within the cell structures are scarcer and the subgrains are not as dense as those previously presented. Remarkably, around the crack tips no slip bands or heavy dislocation activity is observed.

Figure 2-8: Higher magnification TEM images of the Cu metallization after 10000 cycles. The red arrows in (a) and (b) highlight the difference in the cell structure that qualitatively look less dense than those previously presented (cp. to Figs 2.2 and 2.4). (a) and (c) clearly show the lack of classical fatigue features such as slip bands or dislocations around the pores/cracks.

2.1.3 Comparison of dislocation density before and after pulsed heating

As presented in the previous sections, the most remarkable differences in the dislocation structure after the aging cycles is the formation of the cells, then the sub-grain network, and the decrease of free mobile dislocations in their centre. It could be hypothesized that the effect of aging is the gradual reorganization of the cell structure during the repetitive heating cycles (Figure 2-9).

Figure 2-9: Evolution of dislocation density in cell walls and cell interiors with thermo-mechanical cycling.

To quantify this observation, the dislocation density of the pristine and cycled films are measured. In this report, TEM has been mainly used in the conventional bright field mode to image the grain structure. We also used it to determine the thickness of the foils to allow an estimation of the local volume in which a total dislocation length is measured. The dislocation density is then calculated at the total dislocation length divided by the volume in which this length is measured.

Local thickness was measured using two techniques:

- 1-Counting the thickness fringes for a known diffraction vector (g), and using tabulated extinction distances (Edington, 1975).
- 2-Using the projected thickness of known planar defects such as (111) twins

Both techniques imply tilting experiments and the construction of a stereographic projection to access the local thickness. To gain further insight, and because the interior of the cells shows a much lower density than their walls, densities were calculated inside the cells and in the cell walls (Fig. 2.9).

On average, for each foil, three grains were used to estimate the dislocation density. Figure 2-10 is an example of the calculation of the dislocation density from three grains in the pristine, 2,000 cycles and 10,000 cycles foils respectively. The table beneath each image shows the estimated dislocation density calculated from these zones, which are either the cell walls (red dashed rectangles ρ_w) or the free dislocations within the cell walls (black dashed rectangles ρ_f). The values presented in each table are calculated average of 2-3 images of the same grain from different tilts.

Figure 2-10: Example of a dislocation density estimation in Cu metallization (a) pristine ("as-received") (b) after 2,000 cycles and (c) 10,000 cycles. The dislocation density calculation was separated between the free dislocations and those of the cell walls. As the number of cycles increases, the free dislocation density decreases and the one in the cell walls tend to increase.

The initial values of the dislocation density obtained as a function of the number of thermal aging cycles support our hypothesis. Figure 2-10 highlights that the free dislocation density reduces while that of the cell wall structure increases as the number of cycles increases.

Roughly, the initial "free" dislocation density is around $4 \cdot 10^{11} \text{ m}^{-2}$ and decreases to $2 \cdot 10^{11} \text{ m}^{-2}$ after 10 000 cycles. On the contrary, the dislocation density in cell walls seems to increase first from about $10 \cdot 10^{11} \text{ m}^{-2}$ (initial) to $15\text{-}20 \cdot 10^{11} \text{ m}^{-2}$ (2000 cycles) before eventually decreasing again to $10 \cdot 10^{11} \text{ m}^{-2}$ after 10 000 cycles. One can rationalize this behaviour by assuming that the free dislocations first move to the cell walls, both depleting the centers and densifying the walls. The overall decrease at 10 000 cycles may reflect the annealing process that can take place in the walls by recombination of dislocation dipoles.

Obviously, these measurements are very local, therefore they require a more statistical meaningful measurement campaign, which are very tedious to carry out manually, to present numeral data which could be compared to Dark Field X-Ray Microscopy (DFXM) carried out in WP3 (X-Ray) of the project. TEM measurement have the advantage to be able to separate dislocation densities in cell walls and cell interiors, which is not currently accessible with DFXM. On the other hand, X-Ray measurements provide a statistically meaningful value, that is an average of the rotations produced by dislocations (GND- Geometrically Necessary Dislocations). TEM is returning all the dislocation density (GND+SSD-Statistically Stored Dislocations) and again, a direct comparison of the numbers returned by both methods should take this aspect into account. One may expect that after a long exposure to thermal cycles, and because dislocation slip activity is very low in these Cu metallizations, only GNDs remain at the end in cell walls, and that the cell wall dislocation density at 10 000 cycles, only containing GNDs, reflect perfectly its misorientation.

The local misorientation carried by the cell walls inside a grain is investigated in the next paragraph.

2.2 Grain orientation investigation and chemical segregation

Orientation analysis of sub-grain structure

We performed crystallographic orientation maps on a Cu foil aged to 2000 cycles to investigate the misorientation of these cell structures formed after aging. This investigation was performed using the scanning TEM and its automatic crystallographic orientation mapping (ACOM). The misorientation between these cell structures was found to be low (on the order of 1°), meaning that they pertain to the same 'mother' grain.

Figure 2-11: (a) IPF X micrograph of Cu metallization cycled to 2000 cycles. (b) Band contrast image that highlights three zones with cell structures (c) Low misorientations corresponding to the different zones.

So far, we have only measured misorientation on extracted foils at different steps in the thermomechanical ageing, precluding a direct conclusion on how a given cell wall (or sub-grain) evolves during cycling. To do this, the misorientation evolution during thermal cycling should be monitored on a single feature (cell wall, sub-grain). This is planned for the later stages of the project using in-situ TEM.

Crack path investigation

A second crystallographic map was obtained from the Cu foil aged to 10,000 cycles. The goal was to elucidate on the crack propagation path. Figure 2-12 is an example of a foil extracted from the 'panflute' polyheater where a crack propagated from the surface down to the diffusion barrier. The IPF X map shows that the crack propagates mainly along grain boundaries as is shown by the lack of corresponding orientation along the crack path. As aforementioned, there are some rare cases where the crack seems to propagate within a grain as highlighted in figure 2-12(c). There, the crystallographic profile along line 1 across the crack shows identical orientation after crack propagation.

Figure 2-12: (a) Conventional TEM image of a Cu foil cycled to 10000 cycles. (b) corresponding IPF X map showing two different crack propagation paths with lines 1&2 along which misorientation is measured in c) and d) (c) misorientation of the crack along line 1 on image (b), here the crack is seen to propagate through the grain (no or low misorientation along 1). (d) misorientation of the crack along line 2, which shows that the crack propagates through the grain boundary (large misorientations across the line).

Chemical segregation investigation

During the electrochemical deposition of copper films, impurities (chlorine, oxygen, carbon and sulphur) are incorporated to the metallization. One of the current hypotheses is that, as the cycling progresses, these impurities accumulate along the grain boundaries and are a factor contributing to their embrittlement. It may also explain why limited grain growth is observed in these films during thermomechanical ageing. This in turn may result to intergranular cracking because tensile stresses cannot be accommodated by grain boundary plasticity (grain rotation, shear coupling migration, sliding), nor by dislocation activity that proved to be extremely limited.

An initial EDX chemical analysis was performed on a pristine foil and on a 2000 cycles aged foil. Figure 2-13 displays an ultrathin lamella from the latter, where a grain boundary containing a pore was chosen as the region of interest for a chemical analysis. At this resolution the analysis shows a

very low atomic content of chlorine (within the error margin of the technique: $\approx 0.5\%$) and no particular concentrations along the grain boundaries.

Figure 2-13: Chemical investigation of the potential segregation of chemical elements within a cycled Cu foil. (a) SEM image of an ultrathin TEM lamellae -EDX analysis performed in the green rectangle (b-c) STEM micrographs of the region around the pore that was investigated. (d) EDX chemical maps around the pore region, at this level of accuracy the presence of chlorine is barely detected.

2.3 In situ TEM investigation

In-situ TEM heating was chosen to mimic part of the thermomechanical stress endured by the Cu metallization during electrical ageing and to monitor the potential microstructural changes induced by this type of stress. Considering a copper metallization layered on a Si substrate, the mechanical stress results from temperature swings and the CTE (coefficient of thermal expansion) difference between Cu and Si. With Cu being the softest material, plastic deformation should be mostly accommodated by the metallization. We used the TEM in conventional mode (bright field) to follow the dislocations and grain boundaries evolution inside the Cu metallization during the temperature cycles.

There are several differences between the in-situ TEM heating and the heat pulses in semiconductor applications (or full polyheaters set-ups)

- Due to the size of the TEM cross-section sample, thermal mechanical stresses are expected to be much lower and thus the plastic deformation will initiate at higher temperatures in comparison to what is recorded in the wafer curvature experiments.

- The heating rate (20°C/min) is much slower during TEM heating in comparison to the pulse heating (200ms).
- There is no precise way to measure the stresses in the film during the in-situ TEM heating and cooling.

2.3.1 In situ heating in a pristine polyheater

The TEM cross section sample that was used here was prepared by mechanical polishing. The dimensions are as shown in the Figure 1-5. The sample was heated and cooled between 25°C and 480°C by increments of 100°C. The first cycle takes 40 minutes i.e. the time to heat up to 480°C and completely cool the lamella to RT, the subsequent cycles are usually faster because of less dislocation motion. The TEM CCD camera is connected to a recording device that records a movie of the evolution of the structure during the cycle. Several snapshots were taken during the experiment and presented in Figure 2-14.

Figure 2-14: In situ TEM thermal cycling of a pristine foil prepared by tripod polishing. The heating cycle was set from 25°C to 480°C at 20°C/min. (a) initial dense and tangled dislocation structure with some irradiation artefacts from the ion polishing (small loops - dots). (b-c) after heating to 400 and 480°C the structure remains the same but the irradiation loops have escaped through the free foil surfaces. (d) snapshot taken during cooling: the dislocation structure remains mostly unaffected. Only a slight reduction of density may be observed.

Some dislocations start disappearing from the thin foil through the free surfaces at around 150°C. At 270°C the dislocation motion initiates through very short jumps that are in the range of a few tens of nm. These are hardly noticeable in bright field and do not overcome the cell length scale. This could correspond to the yield stress observed in stress-temperature curves. The following dislocation motion remain extremely limited, meaning that the plastic deformation of the film through dislocation activity is very low. At 480°C, which was the maximum temperature of the cycle, we can qualitatively

observe that the dislocation density had slightly reduced compared to the initial state, but this may be helped by the presence of free surfaces in the TEM lamella configuration. Note that a dislocation density decrease has also been evidenced in post-mortem observations.

During the cooling cycle, the dislocations remain unchanged. At 300°C some dislocations are seen to move, but again, over very short distances. Two other cycles were performed on the same sample, but during these subsequent cycles little or no moving dislocations were observed.

2.3.2 *In situ heating of a cycled polyheater (2000 cycles)*

The TEM sample that was heated in this case was prepared by FIB and the final thinning performed by ion polishing. The sample configuration is given below. The same heating rate and cooling rate are applied.

Figure 2-15: In situ TEM sequence showing the large intra-cell volumes accessible to mobile dislocations in a cycled film and the reverse motion of a curved dislocation attesting of a stress evolution similar to the full polyheater configuration (curved upward on heating-b), and downward on cooling-c).

As previously mentioned in section 2.1, the microstructure of the cycled metallization has less mobile dislocations inside the cells and a well-defined cell structure. It is thus easier to follow the few free dislocation motions as shown in Figure 2-15. During the heating cycle, the dislocation motion starts at about 200°C, some of the dislocations are seen to move towards the grain boundaries and the cell walls where they are trapped while other escape through the film surfaces. At 300°C The dislocations move larger distances in comparison to the as-received foils and as a result slip traces are observed and slip system may be defined. At 480°C, some dislocations are seen to bow in the opposite direction that they were initially, attesting that, despite a reduced stress amplitude, the positive (tension) or negative (compression) state is reproduced in the in-situ TEM foil. During the cooling cycle, the dislocations are seen to return to their initial position. Over the two consecutive cycles that were performed the structure remained unchanged. The last two observations confirm that dislocation plasticity plays a minor role in the overall microstructure changes, especially the most critical ones: pore nucleation and crack propagation. The only mechanism left to explain those therefore lie in an accelerated self-diffusion of Cu atoms and vacancies at the GBs.

Chapter 3 Summary and Conclusion

The effect of the thermomechanical stresses on the microstructure of the Cu films has been investigated both by EBSD and SEM, and also by post-mortem and in-situ TEM.

EBSD and SEM established that ageing of the Cu metallizations occurred through the development of intergranular cracks, and that the grain microstructure did not show major changes.

The post-mortem conventional TEM investigation clearly shows that the slight microstructural changes in the initial cycles consist in the formation of sub-grain boundaries and pore nucleation. The former may result from localized dislocation rearrangements, while the latter should be attributed to accelerated GB diffusion. After 10,000 cycles the sub-grains also became scarcer as pores grow larger and coalesce to create cracks.

The in-situ TEM confirmed that the initial dislocation structure is rather stable due to dislocation movements of very limited amplitude. This limitation is due to their entanglements with other potentially free dislocations and also with initial cell walls. This low dislocation activity cannot be held responsible for pore formation or growth, but it is densifying the cell walls while depleting their centres. The cells interior slowly clears out of entangled dislocation, becoming volumes where free dislocations can move more easily. Indeed, in-situ heating of aged films shows more ample dislocation movements. These moves remain limited by the cell size, though, and this dislocation activity remains far below what would be needed to reorganize the structure in smaller cells for instance. Overall, the free dislocation density decreases with cycling, while cells densify and may transform progressively in LAGBs or sub-grain boundaries. This is sketched in Fig. 3.1.

Figure 3-1: Sketch of the dislocation structure evolution over cycling in Cu metallizations

Pores are definitely not created by intense dislocation activity, and so the cracks, as no active slip system or slip bands was detected near either of them. Other deformation mechanisms such as GB diffusion must be taken responsible for this type of damage. Alternative mechanisms such as GB sliding, shear-coupling GB migration or grain rotation are also unlikely to have a major role as the overall grain structure is conserved, only for their interior to undergo slight re-arrangements (cell densification).

Chapter 4 Outlook

As the dislocation plasticity was less important than anticipated in the deformation mechanisms affecting the microstructure of Cu lines and films, in-situ TEM investigation proved essential to detect these subtle changes. We plan to extend it to the study of misorientations at the cell wall level and to obtain dislocation density numbers in a more statistical way. Machine learning or computer vision methods would actually be welcome to help in this matter. These measurements should help us converging on actual dislocation density numbers, validated both by electron microscopy (WP4) and X-Ray techniques (WP3), to be used by the modelling group (WP5).

The in-situ TEM technique proved complex to enable as the Cu metallization is rather thick (20 μ m) compared to the scale of regular TEM samples, especially when a significant thickness of substrate is also needed to account for the thermomechanical effects (CTE difference between Si and Cu). To provide a better ground for these thermomechanical effects, a novel in-situ TEM polyheater has been developed by KAI. This specimen has just been delivered to CEMES and should be thinned down to e-transparency before being wired and in-situ tested on a multi-contact TEM sample holder.

Along with plain Cu films mimicking the microstructure of Cu metallizations, new tests will also serve to spot the mechanisms responsible for pore nucleation and growth. Those will involve creep and fatigue tests at medium temperature, both on plain Cu films (mechanically stressed in tension on dedicated HT straining holders) and novel in-situ polyheaters (stressed in fatigue by current injection).

Chapter 5 List of Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Translation
ACOM	Automated crystallographic orientation mapping
CTE	Coefficient of Thermal Expansion
EBSD	Electron Backscatter Diffraction
ECD	Electrochemically deposited
EDX	Energy Dispersive Xray spectroscopy
GB	Grain boundary
HAGBs	High angled grain boundaries
IPF (X, Y, Z)	Inverse Pole Figure (along X, Y or Z direction)
FIB	Focused Ion Beam
HT, RT	High Temperature, Room Temperature
KAM	Kernel Average Misorientation
LAGBs	Low angle grain boundaries
SEM	Scanning Electron Microscopy
TEM	Transmission Electron Microscopy

Chapter 6 Bibliography

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